

Suitability of sodium-ion-based battery pack as a cold-start alternative to a conventional 12 V/15 Ah lead-acid starter battery

Tomas Finsterle¹ · Jan Kasper¹ · Vaclav Knap¹ · Pavel Hrzina¹

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Abstract

This study presents an experimental evaluation of a sodium-ion battery pack constructed from 18650-format cells compared to a conventional lead-acid starting, lighting, and ignition (SLI) battery. With sodium-ion technology emerging as a promising alternative to lithium-ion and lead-acid chemistries, offering advantages in resource availability, cost-effectiveness, and cold-temperature performance, its potential for various applications warrants detailed investigation. A 4s11p sodium-ion SLI battery pack was assembled for this purpose and subjected to performance testing in a climate chamber across a temperature range from +25 to −15 °C. The results aim to assess the cold-weather reliability and operational viability of sodium-ion cells relative to traditional battery solutions.

Graphical abstract

Keywords Batteries · Lithium-ion · Sodium-ion · Electrochemistry

Introduction

The performance of conventional lead-acid starting, lighting, and ignition (SLI) batteries deteriorates significantly at low temperatures, leading to reliability issues in automotive and backup power applications [1]. As temperature decreases, electrolyte viscosity increases, diffusion coefficients fall, and internal resistance rises sharply, limiting both available capacity and cranking power [2]. Although decades of optimization have improved their robustness, the intrinsic electrochemistry of the Pb/PbO₂ couple leaves little room

for further improvement. In cold climates, oversizing or pre-heating of the batteries is therefore required, increasing system mass and complexity [3].

Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries can provide higher specific energy and longer lifetime than other rechargeable systems; however, their performance remains limited at low temperatures [4]. The sluggish transport of Li⁺ across the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) and the low ionic conductivity of carbonate-based electrolytes, many of which freeze at temperatures below approximately −30 °C, cause a steep voltage drop and rapid capacity loss [5]. In addition, charging at low temperatures may lead to the deposition of metallic lithium, resulting in irreversible capacity fade and internal short circuits. Together with the high cost and limited availability of key materials, such as Li, Ni, and Co, these factors restrict the applicability of Li-ion technology in large-scale or cost-sensitive

✉ Tomas Finsterle
finsttom@fel.cvut.cz

¹ Department of Electrotechnology, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University, Prague, Czech Republic

applications. Sodium-ion batteries (SIB) are emerging as a promising alternative. Unlike lithium, sodium is abundant, inexpensive, and can be processed on the same production lines as Li-ion cells. Recent studies have shown that commercially available cylindrical SIB cells, particularly in the 18650 format, can achieve specific energies above 120 Wh kg⁻¹, lifetimes exceeding 2000 cycles [6], and stable performance even at sub-zero temperatures [7]. The chemical composition of these cells varies by manufacturer, but typically includes a hard-carbon anode and cathodes based on layered metal oxides, polyanionic phosphates or Prussian blue analogs [8].

Despite the rapidly growing interest in sodium-ion battery technology, the low-temperature behavior of SIB systems has only recently begun to receive systematic attention. Several studies have shown that the electrochemical performance of SIBs deteriorates markedly at sub-zero temperatures due to sluggish Na⁺ diffusion in electrode materials and reduced ionic conductivity in the electrolyte, which together impose strong kinetic limitations on interfacial charge transfer processes [9].

In addition to bulk transport limitations, the stability and formation of the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) in SIBs are strongly temperature-dependent. At low temperatures, incomplete desolvation of Na⁺, increased electrolyte viscosity, and hindered interfacial transport can significantly increase polarization losses and suppress reversible Na⁺ insertion and extraction [10].

Recent experimental and modeling studies further suggest that sodium-ion systems may exhibit distinct low-temperature failure modes compared to Li-ion batteries, including altered intercalation pathways, surface accumulation of metallic sodium, and changes in the dominant polarization mechanisms under kinetic constraints [11].

To mitigate these intrinsic low-temperature limitations, various strategies have been proposed, including electrolyte formulation with low-freezing-point solvents, interface engineering, and the development of electrode materials with reduced Na⁺ diffusion barriers [12]. However, most of these approaches have so far been demonstrated at the single-cell level, and their relevance for multi-cell packs operating under high-current pulses remains largely unexplored.

Beyond materials abundance, SIB technology offers several technical advantages: it can use aluminum current collectors on both electrodes, eliminating the need for copper and reducing cost and weight, while improving recyclability [13].

In contrast to Li-ion systems, lithium-metal plating is not relevant for sodium-ion batteries. However, metallic sodium deposition on the anode surface (so-called sodium plating) has been reported under specific operating conditions, particularly at low temperatures and high current densities [14]. Such sodium deposition may promote dendritic growth and

represent a potential limiting factor for cold operation if not properly controlled [7].

A key advantage of SIB lies in their behavior under cold conditions. While Na⁺ diffusion within electrode materials is slower than Li⁺ at room temperature, the desolvation process of Na⁺ at the electrode–electrolyte interface requires lower activation energy, partially compensating for the kinetic limitation at low temperatures [5]. As a result, SIB cells may retain comparatively more stable voltage response and charge transfer characteristics under moderately sub-zero conditions.

Despite considerable progress in characterizing single SIB cells, little systematic data exist for multi-cell SIB packs subjected to high-current pulses typical of starter or backup applications. Most published studies focus on constant-current discharge behavior, which does not capture transient voltage response or internal heating during short current surges [4]. However, such dynamic conditions are critical for 12 V SLI systems, where instantaneous discharge currents often exceed 150–200 A [15].

This study therefore investigates a 4s11p SIB pack assembled from 44 commercial 18650 cells (14.3 Ah) and compares its performance with that of a standard 12 V/15 Ah lead-acid SLI battery. Tests were performed in a climate chamber between +25 and –15 °C using 200 A pulses of 3 s duration. This study builds upon prior research on impedance behavior, cell construction and high-current performance [4, 6, 15]. The objective is to evaluate the suitability of SIB technology for starting and backup applications in harsh climatic conditions and to identify operational limits related to temperature and state-of-charge.

Results and discussion

Voltage distribution of cells before and after equalization

The initial voltage measurement of individual SIB 18650 cells upon unpacking from the transport packaging revealed a noticeable spread in values ranging from 1.845 to 2.434 V, with a standard deviation of 0.182 V (Fig. 1, Table 1). This voltage dispersion corresponds to varying state-of-charge (SoC), which can be attributed to storage conditions, manufacturing tolerances, or self-discharge of the cells during logistics. After individually charging the cells to a target voltage of 3.00 V, the voltage levels among all cells equalized, yielding an average value of 2.998 V with a minimal deviation of only ± 0.001 V. This state-of-charge equalization step is crucial for ensuring uniform current load across the cells and preventing overvoltage in weaker ones during cycling. The SoC equalization thus established uniform initial conditions for the subsequent pulse-discharge tests.

Fig. 1 Voltage distribution within the cell assembly before and after equalization (balancing)

Table 1 Statistics of measured voltages before and after balancing

Measurement state	V_{max}/V	V_{avg}/V	V_{min}/V
Before balancing	2.4340	2.1995	1.8450
After balancing	2.9998	2.9984	2.9979

All tested cells were new, unused commercial sodium-ion 18650 cells acquired specifically for this study. The cells were not subjected to any intentional storage by the authors; immediately after delivery, they were inspected, measured, and assembled into the battery pack. No prior cycling history or usage information was available. Consequently, the initially observed voltage dispersion cannot be attributed to aging, degradation, or storage-related effects. Although the magnitude of the voltage spread was somewhat unexpected for a batch of nominally identical new cells, it is interpreted as a state-of-charge (SoC) variation rather than an indication of impaired state-of-health (SoH). This interpretation is supported by the fact that after controlled individual charging, the voltage distribution converged to 2.998 ± 0.001 V, confirming good electrochemical condition and high homogeneity of the tested cells.

Average voltage drop ΔV (V)

The average voltage drop ΔV (defined as the difference between the voltage at the beginning and at the end of the 3-s, 200 A discharge pulse) exhibits a clear dependence on temperature and charging voltage (Fig. 2). As the

temperature decreases, ΔV increases for all systems, reflecting the rise in internal resistance and the slowdown of ionic kinetics.

The highest ΔV values were recorded for the SIB 16 V system at -15 °C (≈ 3.4 V), followed by SIB 14.4 V (≈ 2.0 V) and Pb 14.4 V (≈ 2.2 V). In the moderate temperature range ($+5$ – $+25$ °C), the SIB 16 V system shows the lowest voltage drop (≈ 1.1 – 1.4 V), confirming its superior voltage stability at a sufficiently high state-of-charge.

While at low temperatures the effect of the higher initial voltage in the SIB 16 V system manifested as a larger absolute ΔV , at temperatures above $+5$ °C, the trend reverses: the SIB 16 V exhibits lower polarization losses than both the Pb battery and the undercharged SIB 14.4 V system. At sub-zero temperatures, the higher initial voltage of the 16 V SIB pack resulted in a larger absolute voltage drop (ΔV) compared to both the 14.4 V SIB and the lead-acid system. With increasing temperature, all configurations showed a gradual decrease in ΔV , indicating reduced internal resistance and polarization losses. In the moderate and higher temperature ranges ($+15$ to $+25$ °C), the SIB (16 V) maintained the lowest ΔV among the tested systems, confirming its superior voltage stability under warm conditions.

Number of valid pulses (≥ 3 s) as a function of temperature

A summary of the results is presented in Fig. 3, which shows the number of successful pulses until the voltage drops below 8.4 V. At -15 °C, only the Pb battery remains

Fig. 2 Temperature dependence of the voltage drop ΔV ($0 \rightarrow 3$ s) for Pb (14.4 V) and SIB (14.4 V and 16.0 V)

Fig. 3 Number of valid 200 A pulses (≥ 3 s) before the voltage drops below 8.4 V for Pb and SIB at different temperatures

functional (11 pulses), while both SIB modes fail after the first one. At $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the SIB (16 V) reaches 31 pulses, exceeding Pb (24 pulses), whereas the SIB (14.4 V) achieves only 14. In the $+5$ to $+25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ range, the order remains consistent: SIB 16 V > Pb 14.4 V > SIB 14.4 V. Increasing the charging voltage from 14.4 to 16.0 V thus raises the number of valid pulses by approximately 30–50%.

For comparison, the low-temperature behavior of commercially relevant lithium-ion systems has been extensively investigated. It is well established that, at subzero temperatures, the charge transfer kinetics and ionic conductivity of Li-ion cells decrease markedly, leading to a pronounced increase in internal resistance and a substantial reduction in both available capacity and power output [16]. In addition, low-temperature operation—especially during charging—significantly increases the risk of lithium plating on the anode, which is associated with irreversible capacity loss and safety concerns [17].

Consequently, Li-ion batteries typically exhibit strong performance limitations below $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and their practical use in cold environments often requires pre-heating, thermal management, or oversizing strategies to maintain acceptable power delivery [18]. In this context, the observed abrupt limitation of the tested SIB pack at $-15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is consistent with the general behavior of high-power rechargeable systems operated far below their optimal temperature window. The relative advantage of SIB is therefore primarily observed at moderately sub-zero temperatures when the pack is operated at a sufficiently high state of charge.

Placement of thermocouples and interpretation of temperature profiles

Thermocouples T1–T6 were inserted manually between the cylindrical 18650 cells of the SIB pack (4s11p) without adhesive or mechanical fixation. The sensors were positioned during pack assembly and were held primarily by the mechanical pressure of adjacent cells. A schematic representation of the approximate sensor placement is provided in Fig. 4.

Due to this rapid manual installation method, small variations in insertion depth, local thermal contact, and minor positional shifts during handling cannot be fully excluded. Therefore, the thermocouple readings are interpreted as representative local temperature trends rather than as strictly position-defined absolute temperatures.

Sensors T1–T3 were located deeper between the cells, in areas where heat generation and accumulation are expected to be most pronounced. These sensors exhibited a greater cumulative temperature rise (ΔT) and showed initial values $1\text{--}2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ higher than the ambient chamber temperature at the start of the measurement. This offset likely reflects the internal thermal inertia of the pack and incomplete equilibrium

Fig. 4 Schematic representation of the approximate placement of thermocouples T1–T6 within the 4s11p SIB pack

after placement in the climatic chamber. The time evolution of these temperatures is particularly evident in Fig. 5 ($+25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and Fig. 6 ($-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), where gradual heating of the inner sensors during the pulse series can be observed.

T5 and T6 were positioned closer to the outer cells and terminals, i.e., in regions with more effective heat transfer to the surroundings. These sensors recorded smaller temperature increases during the pulse sequence, while their initial values corresponded to the ambient temperature ($-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $+25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Their stable profiles without significant accumulation are also evident in the referenced graphs.

Sensor T4 exhibited a different behavior compared to the other thermocouples. During each current pulse, its temperature increased briefly and then returned close to its baseline during the subsequent rest period, resulting in a non-cumulative temperature profile. Since the pack remained mechanically stable during the experiments, this behavior is most plausibly attributed to the initial placement of T4 during pack assembly, which may have resulted in weaker thermal coupling to the surrounding cells and enhanced local heat dissipation.

Importantly, the T4 signal remained stable and reproducible throughout the experiment and clearly resolved the pulsed heating pattern Fig. 5. The overall thermal behavior of the pack was evaluated using the complete set of thermocouples, and the atypical response of a single sensor does not affect the main conclusions regarding temperature non-uniformity and self-heating under high-current pulse loading.

The resulting temperature distribution confirms the presence of measurable gradients between the center and the periphery of the pack, reaching several degrees Celsius under high-current conditions. The recorded profiles provide valuable insights into the thermal dynamics of the assembly and offer a consistent explanation for the observed voltage-drop (ΔV) behavior and its dependence on local temperature effects.

Experimental verification in a vehicle

The 4s11p SIB pack was connected directly to the starting system of a Škoda Fabia 1.4 MPI vehicle, as shown in

Fig. 5 Temperature profiles of T1–T6 in the SIB pack at +25 °C (charged to 16 V)

Fig. 6 Temperature profiles of T1–T6 in the SIB pack at -5 °C (charged to 16 V)

Fig. 7. Prior to the vehicle test, the pack was charged to 14.4 V, corresponding to the standard lead-acid charging voltage, in order to ensure compatibility with the existing vehicle electrical system. The test was performed at an ambient temperature of approximately +15 °C. During a series of 20 consecutive engine starts, peak currents

of about 140 A were recorded using a clamp ammeter. The SIB pack enabled repeated engine cranking without failure; after several consecutive starts, a slight reduction in cranking speed was observed, which disappeared after a short engine operation and subsequent warming of the cells.

Fig. 7 Experimental verification of the SIB 4s11p pack installed in the Škoda Fabia 1.4 MPI vehicle for real-world start testing

The physical dimensions of the tested SIB pack were approximately $23 \times 7 \times 8$ cm. These dimensions refer solely to the active cell assembly and do not include the supporting base plate, cabling, or external connectors. For comparison, the vehicle was originally equipped with a conventional 12 V lead-acid starter battery with a nominal capacity of 40 Ah, whereas the tested SIB pack provided a capacity of 14.3 Ah. Despite this substantially lower capacity, the SIB pack successfully enabled repeated engine starts, indicating that peak power capability rather than total stored energy is the critical parameter for short-duration starting events.

Extrapolating the present configuration to a nominal capacity comparable to the original 40 Ah lead-acid battery would require an approximately 2.8-fold increase in cell count and, correspondingly, in pack volume. The vehicle experiment was therefore intended as a functional verification of high-current starting capability under real operating conditions rather than as a direct full-capacity replacement of the original lead-acid battery.

The results confirm that the 4s11p battery pack based on (SIB) cells exhibits operating characteristics distinct from those of a conventional lead-acid starter battery.

In the moderate and higher temperature ranges ($+5$ to $+25$ °C), the fully charged SIB (16.0 V) consistently outperformed the Pb battery, both in terms of voltage stability and the number of successful pulses. This confirms that sodium-ion technology, when operated within its optimal voltage range, can deliver higher instantaneous power density than lead-acid systems of comparable nominal capacity. The smaller voltage drops ΔV at $+15$ °C and $+25$ °C (≈ 1.1 – 1.4 V for SIB 16 V) indicate low polarization and efficient charge transfer, making this chemistry suitable for short-term high-current peaks typical of starter or UPS systems.

At sub-zero temperatures, however, the performance of the SIB decreased rapidly, and neither configuration (14.4 V nor 16.0 V) was able to sustain valid operation at -15 °C. This limitation is therefore not primarily related to the charging voltage or SoC window, but rather to intrinsic transport and kinetic constraints of Na^+ ions within the electrolyte and electrodes at a low temperature. Increased internal resistance and possible inhomogeneities between parallel cells may have further amplified the voltage drop, leading to the immediate cutoff observed after the first pulse. At -5 °C, on the other hand, the SIB (16.0 V) achieved 31 valid pulses compared with 14 for the SIB (14.4 V), confirming that the system retains high-rate capability when ionic mobility remains sufficient and the pack is charged to its full voltage window.

Thermal measurements revealed a non-uniform temperature rise within the pack: the inner thermocouples T1–T3 showed cumulative heating of several degrees Celsius compared to the surroundings. This self-heating partially compensates for the increased internal resistance and can temporarily improve the voltage response during subsequent pulses. Sensor T4 exhibited a distinct trend compared to the other thermocouples, showing the lowest and non-cumulative temperature rise throughout the pulse sequence. Since the thermocouples were only inserted between the cells and not mechanically fixed, a small positional shift or weaker contact cannot be excluded. The observed profile may therefore reflect either a location with more efficient local cooling or a reduced thermal coupling to the surrounding cells. In both cases, the consistently stable readings confirm that the signal was reliable and representative of a region experiencing minimal heat accumulation within the pack.

From an application perspective, the tested 4s11p SIB configuration demonstrates clear potential as a lightweight and maintenance-free alternative for starter or auxiliary power systems operating above 0 °C. However, for low-temperature applications, several improvements are required: (i) optimization of the electrolyte composition to achieve lower viscosity and higher Na^+ conductivity, (ii) implementation of a pre-heating or activation cycle prior to pulse discharge, and (iii) integration of a simple BMS for SoC balancing and thermal protection. These measures could extend the functional temperature range well below 0 °C and enable full replacement of lead-acid SLI systems.

A practical verification was carried out at an ambient temperature of approximately $+15$ °C in a real vehicle (Škoda Fabia 1.4 MPI). A clamp current probe indicated a peak draw of around 140 A during engine start. The pack successfully performed more than 20 consecutive starts without significant performance degradation; after several starts, a slight reduction in engine cranking speed was observed, which disappeared after a short (3–5 s) engine run and warming of the cells. This behavior corresponds to

the laboratory results and confirms the SIB pack's ability to deliver high currents under real operating conditions, along with a beneficial thermal feedback effect due to self-heating.

In summary, sodium-ion batteries can match or even outperform lead-acid systems at temperatures above -5 °C, offering lower polarization and higher voltage stability. Low-temperature limitations remain the main barrier to direct deployment, yet given the environmental and material advantages of sodium chemistry, the results of this study confirm its strong potential for future hybrid or assisted starting applications.

Experimental methods

The experiments were performed using commercial cylindrical 18650-format sodium-ion cells (model: Hakadi 18650—1300 mAh). According to the manufacturer's specification, the cells have a nominal voltage of 3.0 V and a typical capacity of 1300 mAh (0.2 C, 1.8 V cut-off), with a specified minimum capacity of 1220 mAh and an internal AC impedance below 20 m Ω (1 kHz) [19]. The cells are designed as high-rate types, with a maximum continuous discharge current of 20 C (26 A) and a peak current of up to 30 C (39 A for ≤ 5 s) [19]. The manufacturer specifies an operating discharge temperature range extending down to -40 °C, albeit with strongly reduced allowable C rates, while charging below 0 °C is explicitly not recommended [19]. At -20 °C (0.5 C), a remaining discharge capacity of at least 85% of the minimum rated capacity is reported, decreasing to approximately 48% at -40 °C (0.5 C, 1.8 V cut-off) [19].

The cells were subjected to a range of standard abuse tests, including overcharge, overdischarge, external short-circuit, thermal shock, crush, and impact tests, without fire or explosion [19].

The manufacturer does not publicly disclose detailed materials information such as the specific cathode chemistry, electrolyte composition, separator type, or the precise anode material and solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) characteristics. Consequently, these proprietary details could not be included in the present study.

A total of 44 commercial SIB 18650 cells (Hakadi, nominally 3.0 V/1.3 Ah) were used in this study. Each cell was individually measured using a precision voltmeter with a resolution of 1 mV. Cells whose open-circuit voltage deviated by more than ± 50 mV from the group average were balanced through controlled constant-current charging to ensure a uniform state-of-charge (SOC) across the entire batch.

After balancing, the cells exhibited an average voltage of 2.998 ± 0.001 V, confirming a high level of homogeneity. The resulting 4s11p configuration provides a nominal voltage of approximately 12 V and a theoretical capacity

of 14.3 Ah. Representative appearance of the Hakadi cells is shown in Fig. 8.

Assembly of the SIB pack

Four 18650 cells were connected in series to form one fundamental module with a nominal voltage of approximately 12 V. 11 identical series modules were then connected in parallel, yielding a complete battery system with a 4s11p configuration, as illustrated in Fig. 9. This topology provides a balance between increased capacity, high current capability, and electrical stability among the parallel branches.

Electrical interconnections between cells were made using nickel strips of 8 mm \times 0.12 mm cross section, spot-welded with a dual-electrode handheld welder. The same material was used for series joints to minimize resistive and thermal imbalance. Mechanical stability was ensured by plastic 18650 cell holders, which also provided consistent spacing and thermal distribution during operation.

To ensure safe operation at discharge currents up to 200 A, power leads with a minimum cross section of 10 mm² and connectors rated beyond the maximum load current were used. The pack was mounted on a thermally insulated plastic base and reinforced to prevent deformation during handling. No battery management system (BMS) or integrated temperature sensors were included; voltage and current were monitored externally using the test instrumentation, as depicted in Fig. 10.

Fig. 8 Commercial Hakadi 18650 SIB cells (3.0 V/1.3 Ah) used for the construction of the battery pack

Fig. 9 Assembly process of the 4s11p SIB battery pack consisting of 44 Hakadi 18650 cells, shown from multiple perspectives

Fig. 10 Experimental setup showing the 4s11p SIB pack and the reference lead-acid SLI battery placed inside the climatic chamber during testing

Test plan and conditions

All tests were carried out in a programmable climatic chamber with a temperature control accuracy of ± 0.5 °C. The test matrix included five temperature points: +25 °C, +15 °C, +5 °C, -5 °C, and -15 °C.

Two charging regimes were applied:

1. 14.4 V—corresponding to the lead-acid standard (“undervoltage” mode for the SIB pack),
2. 16.0 V—representing the full charge of the SIB pack.

At each temperature, the pack was subjected to repeated discharge pulses of 200 A for 3 s each, until the voltage dropped below 8.4 V or a safety cut-off was triggered. The reference lead-acid battery (12 V/15 Ah) was tested under identical conditions and charging voltage (14.4 V).

Each test cycle consisted of:

- an initial stabilization rest = 30 s (once, before the first pulse),
- a repeating loop of CC discharge pulses = 3 s (200 A) labeled “CC DChg,”
- followed by rest = 5 min (00:05:00) at open circuit,

- evaluation of the voltage drop ΔV within each 3-s pulse,
- counting valid pulses (≥ 3 s) until failure, defined as pack voltage falling below 8.4 V.

Instrumentation and data acquisition

All measurements were performed using a Neware CE-6000 battery test system, rated for 60 V/200 A per channel. This system is designed for dynamic high-current applications and provides synchronous logging of voltage, current, and time with a temporal resolution of 1 s as set in the test program.

The climatic chamber was controlled by a feedback loop, and after each temperature change, the pack was kept under stable conditions for at least 12 to 24 hours to ensure full thermal equilibrium before starting a new pulse sequence. Each pulse lasted 3 s, and the voltage and current profiles were recorded in 1-s intervals. Data were subsequently processed in MATLAB, where ΔV , V_{end} , and 30-s recovery voltages were extracted. From these datasets, the dependence of the number of valid pulses on temperature was evaluated, followed by statistical analysis of the results.

Since part of the measurements were conducted at 14.4 V (Pb standard regime) and part at 16.0 V (fully charged SIB

pack), the results were interpreted with respect to the effect of charging voltage on cold-temperature performance. This approach enabled a direct comparison of real-world (Pb-compatible) and optimal (nominal) SIB operating regimes.

Real-world verification in vehicle application

In addition to the laboratory measurements in the climatic chamber, a practical verification test was conducted in a passenger car to evaluate the ability of the 4s11p SIB pack to deliver high-current pulses under real operating conditions. The pack was temporarily installed in a Škoda Fabia 1.4 MPI vehicle and used as a direct starter power source at ambient temperature (+ 15 °C).

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Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest. The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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